

Towards optimal resource management in solar thermal applications: CSP and desalination

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Towards optimal resource management in solar thermal applications: CSP and desalination

Introduction

Part One: Optimal water and electricity management in a combined cooling system

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Context

Improved material conditions

Unequal and non-distributed fossil growth

Consequences are externalized to the Global South and to the future

Technology can't save us

Global mean temperature 1850-2024

Difference from 1850-1900 average

— Berkeley Earth (1850-2024.12) — ERA5 (1940-2024.12) — GISTEMP (1880-2024.12) — HadCRUT5 (1850-2024.12) — JRA-3Q (1947-2024.12) — NOAA GlobalTemp v6 (1850-2024.12)

Annual global mean temperature anomalies relative to a pre-industrial (1850-1900) baseline shown from 1850 to 2024

Chart: WMO · Created with Datawrapper

Context

| About this research work

- Technology can't save us but...
- This research work contributes within a –technological development– limited scope:

Developing and improving two solar-driven processes by intelligent resource management:

Part One: Cooling in CSP | Water → Energy

Part Two: Thermal desalination | Energy → Water

A central element of this contribution is the digitalization / automation of these systems through:

- Modelling and
- Optimization

Introduction | Context: Cooling in CSP - Desalination - Method: Modelling - Optimization

Part One

Part Two

Final Part

Cooling in CSP

Context

| Solar thermal energy and water Concentrated Solar Power (CSP)

Parabolic-through experimental facility at PSA

Concentrating Solar Power Gen3 Demonstration Roadmap, U.S. Department of Energy

Gemasolar. Seville, Spain

Context

| Solar thermal energy and water Power cycle cooling

Concentrating Solar Power Gen3 Demonstration Roadmap, U.S. Department of Energy

Context

| Solar thermal energy and water Conventional cooling technologies

WCT (Wet Cooling Tower)

lower capital costs
power-cycle increased efficiency
significant water use (1.8–4 l/kWh)

Concentrating Solar Power Gen3 Demonstration Roadmap, U.S. Department of Energy

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lower capital costs
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DC (Dry Cooling)

high capital costs (3.5–4.5x)
lower power-cycle efficiency
(1.5–5x kW/kWh and 5–6% penalty)
no water use

Context

| Solar thermal energy and water

Current and future perspective

Power cycle cooling is associated either with high water use or limited efficiency.

Questions **profitability** and **sustainability**

WCT: 55 %
DC: 24 %
(Worldwide)

WCT: 94 %
DC: 4 %
(Spain)

Greater potential for solar-powered processes

Takes place in water-scarce regions

Context

| Cooling in CSP

Alternative cooling solutions

WCT (Wet Cooling Tower)

lower capital costs
power-cycle increased efficiency
significant water use (1.8–4 l/kWh)

Hybrid / combined cooling systems integrate **dry** and **wet** components

DC (Dry Cooling)

high capital costs (3.5–4.5x)
lower power-cycle efficiency
(1.5–5x kW/kWh and 5–6% penalty)
no water use

Context

| Cooling in CSP

Alternative cooling solutions

Many heterogeneous hybrid/combined coolers can be found depending on the water saving target:

DC

0%
water
use

5-15 % water use*

WCT

100%
water
use

15-85 % water use*

*compared to only-WCT

They provide flexibility to adapt the system operation to the changing conditions

Objective

| Part One: Cooling in CSP

Efficient management of water resources in CSP plants by optimization of a novel combined cooling system

Introduction | Context: Cooling in CSP - **Desalination** - Method: Modelling - Optimization

Part One

Part Two

Final Part

Thermal desalination

Context

| Desalination

Water scarcity

- 51 countries will suffer from high water stress by 2050^[1]
- Priority: Reduce and Reuse/Recycle but not enough
- Desalination already plays a fundamental role in many regions and demand is expected to increase

Challenges

- Increase process efficiency
- Couple with renewables
- Reduce discharges (Minimum Liquid Discharge, MLD) and generate added value from separation process (brine mining)

[1] World Resources Institute (2023)

Context

| Thermal desalination

Multi-Effect Distillation (MED) Working principle

Multi-Effect Distillation is a thermal desalination technology.

It produces freshwater out of seawater by using heat (and electricity)

Its separation principle is through **evaporation**

Context

| Thermal desalination

Multi-Effect Distillation (MED) Working principle

Multi-Effect Distillation is a thermal desalination technology.

It produces freshwater out of seawater by using heat (and electricity)

Its separation principle is through **evaporation**

Comparison of WFI Production Methods, Bioprocess Online (Feb 2025)

Context

| Desalination technologies

Potential of thermal desalination

New applications

- Minimum Liquid Discharge (MLD)
- Brine mining
- **Industrial / mining water treatment**

Alternative (variable) energy sources

- Waste heat: 20–50% primary energy wasted^[1,2]
- Solar thermal: standalone or co-generation^[3]

- MED is a resilient and adaptable technology
- Potential where waste heat is available and with high salinity streams
- Hybrid desalination: RO + MED
- Thermal systems are more recyclable

[1] Brückner et al. (2015), "Industrial Waste Heat Recovery Technologies"
[2] Elsaied et al. (2020), "Recent Progress on the Utilization of Waste Heat for Desalination"
[3] Palenzuela et al. (2019), "Concentrating Solar Power and Desalination Plants"

Context

| Thermal desalination

Different applications

MED with Thermal Vapor Compression (MED-TVC) units each of 5,000 m³/day capacity, Abu Qir Thermal Power Plant, Egypt

MED for Water for Injection (WFI) Production, MECO

Desalination, high quality water purification

Objective

| Part Two: Thermal Desalination

Efficient use of solar energy for clean water production in a solar-driven multi-effect distillation (MED) system with thermal storage

Introduction | Context: Cooling in CSP - Desalination - Method: Modelling - Optimization

Part One

Part Two

Final Part

Method

Method

| Modelling

First–principles

- ↑ Scalability
- ↑ Interpolate / extrapolate well
- ↓ Computation requirements
- ↓ Vectorization capabilities

Data–driven

(Gaussian Process Regression)

- ↓ Very specific
- ↓ Data requirements
- ↑ Computational efficiency

Method

| Modelling

First–principles

- ↑ Scalability
- ↑ Interpolate / extrapolate well
- ↓ Computation requirements
- ↓ Vectorization capabilities

Data–driven

(Gaussian Process Regression)

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Method

| Modelling

First-principles and Data-driven

First-principles

- ↑ Scalability
- ↑ Interpolate / extrapolate well
- ↓ Computation requirements
- ↓ Vectorization capabilities

Data-driven

(Gaussian Process Regression)

- ↓ Very specific
- ↓ Data requirements
- ↑ Computational efficiency

Discrete modelling through **FSMs**

Simple traffic light

Method

Tries to find the best solution to a problem under given circumstances

Amini, Alexander, Ava Soleimany, Sertac Karaman, and Daniela Rus. "Spatial Uncertainty Sampling for End-to-End Control." arXiv:1805.04829. Preprint, arXiv, May 24, 2019

| Optimization

Optimization algorithms

Method

| Optimization

Problem types and optimization algorithms

Tries to find the best solution to a problem under given circumstances.

Problem types Non-Convex NLP

Method

Tries to find the best solution to a problem under given circumstances.

Problem types Non-Convex NLP

| Optimization

Problem types and optimization algorithms

Algorithms. Global search optimization

Heuristic Algorithms:

- Genetic
- Evolutionary
- PSO
- Simulated annealing
- CMA-ES
- etc

Method

Tries to find the best solution to a problem under given circumstances.

MINLP problems combine combinatorial optimization with non-convex optimization

Problem type Mixed Integer NLP (MINLP)

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Final Part

Introduction

| Power cycle cooling in CSP

Concentrating Solar Power Gen3 Demonstration Roadmap, U.S. Department of Energy

Facility

| Combined cooling

Experimental facility at PSA

Facility

| Combined cooling

Flexibility → Adaptability

Pareto fronts in different representative scenarios

- (I) | 20050623 | $T_{amb}=30.0\text{ °C}$, HR=40 %, $T_v=42.0\text{ °C}$, $\dot{Q}=200\text{ kW}_{th}$
- (II) | 20050623 | $T_{amb}=30.0\text{ °C}$, HR=40 %, $T_v=42.0\text{ °C}$, $\dot{Q}=120\text{ kW}_{th}$
- ◆ (III) | 20051221 | $T_{amb}=10.0\text{ °C}$, HR=70 %, $T_v=42.0\text{ °C}$, $\dot{Q}=200\text{ kW}_{th}$
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Cooling power and hydraulic distribution (III)

Facility

| Combined cooling

Flexibility → Adaptability

Pareto fronts in different representative scenarios

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Cooling power and hydraulic distribution (III)

Objective

| Cooling alternatives comparison

Annual simulation for one case study where operation is optimized to minimize cooling costs given a representative load profile and costs/water availability context.

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{e}; \theta} J^{(n)} = J_e^{(n)} + J_w^{(n)} = f(\underbrace{\mathbf{T}_{amb}, \mathbf{HR}, \dot{\mathbf{Q}}, \mathbf{T}_v, V_{avail,0}}_{\text{Environment, } \mathbf{e}}, \underbrace{\mathbf{P}_e, \mathbf{P}_{w,s1}, \mathbf{P}_{w,s2}, \mathbf{q}_c}_{\text{Economic}}, \underbrace{\mathbf{R}_p, \mathbf{R}_s, \omega_{dc}, \omega_{wct}}_{\text{Decision variables, } \mathbf{x}})$$

Introduction

Part One | Introduction – Objective – **Implementation: Modelling** – Optimization – Results – Summary

Part Two

Final Part

Implementation

Modelling → Optimization

Implementation | Modelling

Implementation

| Modelling

WCT

Based on Poppe's theory

Merkel number as key performance indicator

DC

Based on first law of thermodynamics:

$$\dot{Q}_{released} = \dot{Q}_{absorbed} = \dot{Q}_{transferred}$$

Heat exchange determined from convective heat exchange \propto Empirical Nusselt number

[1] Poppe et al. (1991), "Modeling and Simulation of a Solar Field Based on Flat-Plate Collectors"

[2] Kakac et al. (1986), Handbook of Single-Phase Convective Heat Transfer

Implementation | Modelling

WCT inputs sampling by Grid sampling

Implementation

| Modelling

MAPE | FP: 1.28%, Surrorgate: 1.35%

FP: 0.87%, 3.74%, Surrorgate: 1.32%, 4.52%

Implementation | Modelling

Introduction

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Implementation

Optimization

Implementation | Optimization

Multi-stage optimization

- Shrinking horizon optimization that manages the water resource ($V_{avail,0}$) to minimize cooling costs (J)

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{e}; \theta} J^{(n)} = J_e^{(n)} + J_w^{(n)} = f(\underbrace{\underbrace{\mathbf{T}_{amb}, \mathbf{HR}}_{\text{Ambient}}, \underbrace{\dot{Q}, \mathbf{T}_v}_{\text{Th. load}}, \underbrace{V_{avail,0}}_{\text{Water}}, \underbrace{\mathbf{P}_e, \mathbf{P}_{w,s1}, \mathbf{P}_{w,s2}}_{\text{Economic}}, \mathbf{q}_c, \underbrace{\mathbf{R}_p, \mathbf{R}_s}_{\text{Hydraulic conf.}}, \underbrace{\omega_{dc}, \omega_{wct}}_{\text{Comp. cooling}}}_{\text{Environment, } \mathbf{e}}, \underbrace{\phantom{\mathbf{T}_{amb}, \mathbf{HR}, \dot{Q}, \mathbf{T}_v, V_{avail,0}, \mathbf{P}_e, \mathbf{P}_{w,s1}, \mathbf{P}_{w,s2}, \mathbf{q}_c, \mathbf{R}_p, \mathbf{R}_s, \omega_{dc}, \omega_{wct}}}_{\text{Decision variables, } \mathbf{x}})$$

1. Build a set of Pareto fronts

Multi-objective optimization problem

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{e}; \theta} \mathbf{C}_e, \mathbf{C}_w = f(\underbrace{\underbrace{T_{amb}, HR}_{\text{Ambient}}, \underbrace{\dot{Q}, T_v}_{\text{Th. load}}}_{\mathbf{e}}, \underbrace{\mathbf{q}_c, \mathbf{R}_p, \mathbf{R}_s, \omega_{dc}, \omega_{wct}}_{\text{Hydraulic conf. Comp. cooling}}}_{\mathbf{x}})$$

2. Find optimal sequence of operation points

Combinatorial optimization problem over a layered-dynamically weighted graph

$$\min_{\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{e}} J^{(n)} = J_e^{(n)} + J_w^{(n)} = f(\underbrace{V_{avail,0}, \mathbf{P}_e, \mathbf{P}_{w,s1}, \mathbf{P}_{w,s2}, \mathbf{p}}_{\text{Environment } (\mathbf{e})})$$

0. Decompose the problem horizon into its n steps elements.

1. Generate a set of Pareto fronts

Solve a multi-objective optimization problem, independently for each step, to obtain a set of Pareto fronts

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{e}_i; \theta} C_{e,i}, C_{w,i} = f(\underbrace{T_{amb,i}, HR_i, \dot{Q}_i, T_{v,i}}_{\text{Environment (e)}}, \mathbf{x}_i)$$

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2. Path selection subproblem

Select a point on each Pareto front: $\mathbf{p} = (p_1, p_2, \dots, p_{n_{steps}})$ finding a path that minimizes the cumulative cost of operation $J^{(n_{steps})}$

$$\min_{\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{e}} J^{(n)} = f(\underbrace{V_{avail,0}, \mathbf{P}_e, \mathbf{P}_w}_{\text{Environment (e)}}, \mathbf{p})$$

Notes:

- $n \equiv n_{steps}$
- $J^{(k)}$ cum. cost at step k
- Best path

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Introduction

Part One | Introduction – Objective – Implementation: Modelling - Optimization – Results – Summary

Part Two

Final Part

Results

Detailed simulated results → Experimental validation → Annual simulation

February

Cold and wet period

June

Intermediate

September

Hot and dry period

High water availability

Low water availability

February
Cold and wet period

June
Intermediate

September
Hot and dry period

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Low water availability

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Hot and dry period

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Low water availability

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Cold and wet period

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Intermediate

September

Hot and dry period

High water availability

Low water availability

Results

| Experimental validation

Environment data sources and objective

- Electricity cost – Historical pool market price data [1]
- Weather data – Predictions from OpenWeather API
- Thermal load – Arbitrarily decided
- Water context – Fixed available volume at startup [40, L]

Objectives

1. Accurate (water) predictions
2. Autonomous and reliable
3. Resilient and adaptative to planned changes

[1] Red eléctrica 2022

[4] About 8 u.m/l, 2x to 4x beer price

Results

| Experimental validation

Thermal load

10:20

Results

| Experimental validation

- Summer conditions: above 30°C for most of the test
- Weather predictions accurate enough in temperature, worse prediction in humidity
- Water availability was extended until the last moment with very good agreement with predictions
- Robust operation, vapor temperature kept at target*
- Operation successfully adapts to the changing conditions
- Prioritization of dry cooler when lower T_{amb} and lower thermal load
- Overall good agreement between expected outputs and measured ones

Results

| Experimental validation

- Summer conditions: above 30°C for most of the test
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Results

| Optimization

Annual simulation. Context

- Case study: Andasol-II
- Analyzed alternatives
 - WCT only
 - Combined cooler- Scaled up
- Context
 - Electricity cost – Pool market price^[1]
 - Weather data - TMY^[2]
 - Thermal load – From a process model^[3]
 - Water context - 2 sources, 2m³/day max at 0.03 um/m³, 80xP_e^[4]
- Annual simulation

[1] Red eléctrica 2022

[2] Meteonorm V8

[3] Ortega, Bartolomé. "Theoretical analysis of high efficient multi-effect distillation processes and their integration into concentrating solar power plants".

[4] About 8 u.m/l, 2x to 4x beer price

Results

| Annual comparison

- In the WCT-only the alternative water source dominates the cooling cost
- CC provides 48% reduction in water consumption
- More importantly, a 38% water consumption reduction during the most critical period: the driest and hottest months (June – September)

Results

| Annual comparison

- In the WCT-only the alternative water source dominates the cooling cost
- CC provides 48% reduction in water consumption
- More importantly, a 38% water consumption reduction during the most critical period: the driest and hottest months (June – September)
- 80% reduction in cooling costs
- CC alternatives provide stable and cost-effective operation across most of the year, only penalized in the most challenging period and to a much lower degree compared to WCT-only

Summary

- This work addresses challenge of **reducing water consumption** in CSP systems through development of **novel cooling solutions**
- **Detailed** steady–state **modelling** framework: first–principles, data–driven and surrogates with errors below 1°C and 20 l/h in the experimental facility
- **Optimization** strategies are essential for hybrid/combined systems and this work presents the first application of such advanced optimization
- Two–stage multi–objective optimization framework developed and **validated experimentally** to minimize cost of cooling under restricted water scenarios
- The proposed framework **is generic** and can be adapted to other plant designs, locations, and resource scenarios

Towards optimal resource management in solar thermal applications: CSP and desalination

Introduction

Part One: Optimal water and electricity management in a combined cooling system

Part Two: Energy management in MED processes driven by variable energy sources

Final Part

Facility

| Solar desalination

Experimental facility at PSA

Facility

| Solar desalination

Experimental facility at PSA

Solar field Heat exchanger Thermal storage Three-way valve MED plant

Facility

| Solar desalination

Experimental facility at PSA

Facility

| Solar desalination

Experimental facility at PSA

Introduction

Part One

Part Two | Introduction – Objective – Implementation: Modelling - Optimization – Results – Summary

Final Part

Objective

Energy management in MED processes driven by variable energy sources

Objective

Economic optimization problem

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{e}; \boldsymbol{\theta}} J = J_e + J_w = f(\underbrace{\mathbf{I}, \mathbf{T}_{\text{amb}}, \mathbf{T}_{\text{med,c,in}}}_{\text{Environment, } e}, \underbrace{\underbrace{q_{\text{sf}}, q_{\text{ts,src}}}_{\mathbb{R}}, \underbrace{s_{\text{fts,mode}}}_{\mathbb{Z}}}_{\text{sfts}}, \underbrace{\underbrace{q_{\text{med,s}}, q_{\text{med,f}}, \mathbf{T}_{\text{med,s,in}}, \mathbf{T}_{\text{med,c,out}}}_{\mathbb{R}}, \underbrace{\text{med}_{\text{mode}}}_{\mathbb{Z}}}_{\text{med}})$$

Decision variables, \mathbf{x}

Minimize costs (electrical), maximize fresh water production

Objective

| Contributions

Economic optimization problem

Minimize costs (electrical), maximize fresh water production

Decisions on when to start and stop operation
 → MINLP problem

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{e}; \boldsymbol{\theta}} J = J_e + J_w = f(\underbrace{\mathbf{I}, \mathbf{T}_{amb}, \mathbf{T}_{med,c,in}}_{\text{Environment, } e}, \underbrace{\overbrace{q_{sf}, q_{ts,src}}^{\mathbb{R}}, \overbrace{sfts_{mode}}^{\mathbb{Z}}}_{\text{sfts}}, \underbrace{\overbrace{q_{med,s}, q_{med,f}, T_{med,s,in}, T_{med,c,out}}^{\mathbb{R}}, \overbrace{med_{mode}}^{\mathbb{Z}}}_{\text{med}})$$

Decision variables, \mathbf{x}

Objective

Economic optimization problem

Minimize costs (electrical), maximize fresh water production

| Contributions

Decisions on when to start and stop operation

The horizon window should be as long as current decisions affecting future performance

Too short → *Shareholder mentality*. Prioritizing short-term profits leads to overall lower performance

Too long → *Analysis paralysis*. Diminishing returns for excessive computing power.

36 hours or two days of operation shrinking horizon

Introduction

Part One

Part Two | Introduction – Objective – Implementation: Modelling - Optimization – Results – Summary

Final Part

Implementation

Energy management in MED processes driven
by variable energy sources

Implementation

- Hybrid model that orchestrates physics-based models for the solar field, heat exchanger, thermal storage, and three-way valve, plus a data-driven model for the MED unit, along with two supervisory FSMs. Electrical consumptions modelled empirically with poly. models.
- Object-oriented implementation
- Initialization:
 - Initial discrete states (e.g., vacuum generated, etc.)
 - Thermal storage state
 - System parameters (e.g., thermal storage volumes)
- At each step:
 - Environment (I , T_{amb} , $T_{med,c,in}$)
 - Operation decisions

Model 12.8: SolarMED model

$$q_{med,d}, C_e = f(q_{med,s}, q_{med,f}, T_{med,s,in}, T_{med,c,out}, q_{ts,src}, q_{sf}, med_{vac,st}, T_{med,c,in}, T_{amb}, I; \theta_{sf}, \theta_{hx}, \theta_{med}, \theta_{sfts}^{fsm}, \theta_{med}^{fsm}, \theta_{\infty})$$

$$st_{sfts} = sfts\ fsm\ model(q_{sf}, q_{ts,src}; \theta_{sfts}^{fsm})$$

$$st_{med} = med\ fsm\ model(q_{med,s}, q_{med,f}, T_{med,c}; \theta_{med}^{fsm})$$

$$T_{sf,out} = sf\ model(T_{sf,out,k-1}, T_{sf,in,k-n:k}, q_{sf,k-n:k}, I, T_{amb}; \theta_{sf})$$

$$T_{ts,h}, T_{ts,c} = ts\ model(T_{ts,h}(k-1), T_{ts,c}(k-1), T_{hx,s,out}, T_{med,s,out}, q_{ts,src}, q_{ts,dis}, T_{amb}; \theta_{ts})$$

$$T_{sf,in}, T_{hx,s,out} = hx\ model(T_{sf,out}, T_{ts,c,b}, q_{sf}, q_{ts,src}, T_{amb}; \theta_{hx})$$

$$q_{ts,dis} = 3wv\ model(q_{med,s}, T_{med,s,in}, T_{med,s,out})$$

$$q_{med,d}, T_{med,s,out}, q_{med,c}, T_{med,c,out} = med\ model(q_{med,s}, q_{med,f}, T_{med,s,in}, T_{med,c,out}, T_{med,c,in})$$

$$C_{e,sf} = sf\ electrical\ consumption(q_{sf})$$

$$C_{e,ts} = ts\ electrical\ consumption(q_{ts,src})$$

$$C_{e,med} = med\ electrical\ cons.(q_{med,s}, q_{med,f}, q_{med,c}, q_{med,d}, q_{med,b})$$

$$C_e = C_{e,sf} + C_{e,ts} + C_{e,med}$$

Implementation

- The model is evaluated with a sample time of 400 s and four different prediction horizons.
- Static variables such as distillate production ($q_{med,d}$) show no variation with prediction horizon
- Strongly coupled system, errors accumulate over time → Higher error for 8h compared to 1h horizons
- Good agreement between the model predictions and the measurements when all subsystems are active. Higher errors appear during startup and shutdown of the solar field.
- On average, MAPE below 15% for all key variables for 8h-ahead predictions

| Modelling

Predicted variable	Test date	Horizon time (s)	Performance metric		
			MAE (s.u.)	MAPE (%)	Time (s)
$q_{med,d}$ (m ³ /h)	20230414	1800	0.15	16.80	13.42
		3600	0.15	16.80	22.13
		14400	0.15	16.80	8.15
		28800	0.15	16.80	5.86
	20230418	1800	0.07	9.99	7.83
		3600	0.07	9.99	4.52
		14400	0.07	9.99	2.64
		28800	0.07	9.99	2.52
$Q_{ts,h}$ (kWh _{th})	20230414	1800	20.57	15.29	13.42
		3600	17.02	12.65	22.13
		14400	14.90	11.34	8.15
		28800	19.23	15.01	5.86
	20230418	1800	8.73	6.23	7.83
		3600	8.71	6.23	4.52
		14400	16.92	11.64	2.64
		28800	21.01	14.35	2.52
$Q_{ts,c}$ (kWh _{th})	20230414	1800	11.82	6.87	13.42
		3600	14.58	8.17	22.13
		14400	26.15	14.61	8.15
		28800	22.15	12.37	5.86
	20230418	1800	9.30	4.64	7.83
		3600	10.37	5.12	4.52
		14400	21.75	10.76	2.64
		28800	30.39	15.11	2.52

s.u. stands for *same units* as the predicted variable

Implementation

| Optimization

The number of possible operation trajectories ($n_{problems}$) increases exponentially with both the number of integer variables (n_{x_i}) and the number of decision updates ($n_{updates,x_i}$)

$$n_{problems} \approx n_{x_i}^{n_{updates,x_i}}$$

This exponential growth makes the search space extremely large and complex

Problem type Mixed Integer NLP (MINLP)

Implementation

| Optimization

MINLP → nNLP: Operation Plan layer

	Subsystem	Degrees of freedom				n _{problems}
		Day 1		Day 2		
		Start	Stop	Start	Stop	
Evaluation: Start-up (1)	sfts	3	3	1	1	101
	med	3	3	1	1	
Evaluation: Shutdown (2)	sfts	-	3	2	2	144
	med	-	3	2	2	

Operation plan for the different alternatives

sfts: $1 \times [(\text{'start-up'}, 3), (\text{'shutdown'}, 2), (\text{'start-up'}, 1)] + 1 \times [(\text{'shutdown'}, 1)]$
 med: $1 \times [(\text{'start-up'}, 3), (\text{'shutdown'}, 2), (\text{'start-up'}, 1)] + 1 \times [(\text{'shutdown'}, 1)]$

Implementation

| Optimization

MINLP → nNLP: Operation Plan layer

Implementation

| Optimization

Alternative strategies

- **Heuristic**

Rule-based approach to decide when to start and stop the subsystems based on threshold values of the solar irradiance and the thermal storage state of charge.

Operation schedule

- **Solar field:** start when irradiance above 500 W/m^2 , stop when below 400 W/m^2
- **Thermal storage:** start when solar field outlet temperature is above hot tank top temperature
- **MED:** Hot tank top temperature above $76 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, stop when below $65 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

Continuous variables

- **MED** fixed at nominal operation when possible
- **Solar field** fixed outlet temperature setpoint at $90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
- **Thermal storage**

$$\max_{q_{ts,src}; e; \theta} \dot{Q}_{ts,src}$$

subject to: $T_{ts,h,in} > \min(T_{ts,h,t}, 90^\circ\text{C})$

Implementation

| Optimization

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- **MED:** Hot tank top temperature above 76 °C, stop when below 65 °C

Continuous variables

- MED fixed at nominal operation when possible
- Solar field fixed outlet temperature setpoint at 90 °C
- Thermal storage

$$\max_{q_{ts,src};e;\theta} \dot{Q}_{ts,src}$$

subject to: $T_{ts,h,in} > \min(T_{ts,h,t}, 90^{\circ}\text{C})$

- **NLP (non-linear)**

Same as nNLP but with same operation schedule as heuristic alternative

- **nNLP (mixed non-linear)**

(The one proposed in this research work)

nNLP

NLP

Introduction

Part One

Part Two | Introduction – Objective – Implementation: Modelling - Optimization – Results - Summary

Final Part

Results

Case study → Operating strategy comparison → Results comparison

Results

| Case study

- Case study: Simulated PSA experimental plant
- Analyzed alternatives
 - Heuristic
 - NLP: *non-linear*
 - nNLP: *mixed non-linear*

- Context
 - Electricity cost – Constant 0.05 u.m./KWh_e
 - Weather data – Historical data from the plant’s SCADA
 - Water sale price- Constant 3 u.m./m³
- One week-long simulation

Results

| Comparison between alternatives

Results

| Comparison between alternatives

Heuristic

Results

| Comparison between alternatives

Non-linear

Results

| Comparison between alternatives

Mixed non-linear

Results

| Comparison between alternatives

Results

| Comparison between alternatives

Heuristic

Results

| Comparison between alternatives

Non-linear

Results

| Comparison between alternatives

Mixed non-linear

Results

Results

| Comparison between alternatives

- nNLP outperforms NLP and heuristic strategies by **21%** and **32%**

Results

| Comparison between alternatives

- nNLP outperforms NLP and heuristic strategies by 21% and 32%

Optimal operation

- MED at lower temperatures, larger temperature differences
- Long-adaptive operation schedule
- In general, deplete thermal storage

Summary

- Hybrid model of the SolarMED process with multi-hour predictions and MAPE values below 15 % for key process variables

Summary

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- Novel hierarchical optimization strategy to enable autonomous and economically optimal operation
- nNLP outperforms NLP and heuristic strategies by 21% and 32% in a week-long evaluation. Greater benefits expected year-round due to higher environmental variability

Summary

- Hybrid model of the SolarMED process with multi-hour predictions with MAPE values below 15 % for key process variables
- Novel hierarchical optimization strategy to enable autonomous and economically optimal operation
- nNLP outperforms NLP and heuristic strategies by 21% and 32% in a week-long evaluation. Greater benefits expected year-round due to higher environmental variability
- These gains arise from the ability to adapt to the temporal availability of the solar resource using the flexibility provided by thermal storage
- From the nNLP results, NLP and heuristic strategies could be improved

Towards optimal resource management in solar thermal applications: CSP and desalination

Introduction

Part One: Optimal water and electricity management in a combined cooling system

Part Two: Energy management in MED processes driven by variable energy sources

Final Part

Conclusions

Cooling in CSP

- No optimization strategy can fully resolve the intrinsic mismatch between peak cooling demand and water scarcity in hot-dry seasons, the results demonstrate significant remaining potential for improved water management
- CSP plants would benefit by adjusting their generation patterns shifting production away from the hottest hours, when water scarcity and cooling requirements peak, toward evening periods, when cooling is more efficient and renewable supply is lower.

Conclusions

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Solar thermal desalination

- Optimal sensible-driven separation occurs when temperature differences are maximized.
- Primary-energy perspective makes solar-driven MED resemble waste-heat-driven operation.
- Optimal performance requires: long horizon, correct choice of decision variables, flexible operation schedule, and a primary source-aware fitness function

Conclusions

Cooling in CSP

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Solar thermal desalination

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- Optimal performance requires: long horizon, correct choice of decision variables, flexible operation schedule, and a primary source-aware fitness function

Overall

- Two solar processes were modelled and its operation optimized
- The results provide a coherent set of tools and insights for the design and operation of water- and energy-efficient solar-thermal systems

Future work

| Part One: Combined cooling

- Better water management

Additional variables: Reservoir capacity (m^3), Evaporation rate (m^3/h)

Future work

| Part One: Combined cooling

- Better water management
- Improved robustness of low-level control
- Improved Pareto Front computation
- Extend comparison to different configurations and individual cooler sizes

Future work

| Part One: Combined cooling

- Better water management
- Improved robustness of low-level control
- Improved Pareto Front computation
- Extend comparison to different configurations and individual cooler sizes
- Techno-economic analysis

SOLhycool - LCOE comparison between alternatives

Future work

| Part Two: Thermal desalination

- Analyze alternative configurations:

Future work

| Part Two: Thermal desalination

- Analyze alternative configurations:

Derived scientific contributions

Contributions | Publications and conferences

Journal publications

- ▶ J. M. Serrano, P. Navarro, J. Ruiz, P. Palenzuela, M. Lucas, and L. Roca. “Wet Cooling Tower Performance Prediction in CSP Plants: A Comparison between Artificial Neural Networks and Poppe’s Model.” Energy, May 29, 2024, 131844.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2024.131844>.

- ▶ P. Navarro, J. M. Serrano, L. Roca, P. Palenzuela, M. Lucas, and J. Ruiz. “A Comparative Study on Predicting Wet Cooling Tower Performance in Combined Cooling Systems for Heat Rejection in CSP Plants.” Applied Thermal Engineering, June 21, 2024, 123718.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2024.123718>.

- ▶ J. M. Serrano, P. Palenzuela, J. Ruiz, P. Navarro, J. Muñoz, B. Ortega, L. Roca. “Combined cooling for CSP plants: Modeling, experimental validation and optimization analysis” Energy Conversion and Management 348 (January 2026): 120752.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2025.120752>.

Q1
IF 9.4

Q1
IF 6.9

Q1
IF 10.9

Contributions | Publications and conferences

Contribution to conferences

- ▶ J. M. Serrano, J. D. Gil, J. Bonilla, P. Palenzuela, and L. Roca, “Optimal operation of a combined cooling system” in 4th IFAC International Conference on Advances in Proportional-Integral-Derivative Control, Almería, Spain, 2024-06-12/2024-06-14.
- ▶ J. M. Serrano, J. D. Gil Vergel, J. Bonilla, P. Palenzuela, and L. Roca, “Operación óptima de un sistema de refrigeración combinada,” in XLIV Jornadas de Automática, Universidad de Zaragoza, 6, 7 y 8 de septiembre de 2023, Zaragoza, 2023rd ed., Aug. 2023, pp. 477-482.
DOI: [10.17979/spudc.9788497498609.477](https://doi.org/10.17979/spudc.9788497498609.477).
- ▶ P. Navarro, J. M. Serrano, J. Ruiz, M. Lucas, L. Roca, and P. Palenzuela. “Comparison Between an Artificial Neural Network and Poppe’s Model for Wet Cooling Tower Performance Prediction in CSP Plants.” Efficiency, Cost, Optimization, Simulation and Environmental Impact of Energy Systems. International Conference., ECOS 2023, June 25, 2023, 1609–20.
DOI: [10.52202/069564-0146](https://doi.org/10.52202/069564-0146).
- ▶ L. Roca, J. M. Serrano, J.D. Gil, G. Zaragoza, M. Beschi, and A. Visioli. “Modelo de parámetros concentrados para captadores solares planos con reflectores.” Jornadas de Automática, no. 45 (July 2024): 45.
DOI: [10.17979/ja-cea.2024.45.10930](https://doi.org/10.17979/ja-cea.2024.45.10930)

- Two international stays
 - 3 months at UFSC, Florianopolis (Brazil)
 - 1 month at TU Chemnitz, Chemnitz (Germany)

Contributions | Open implementation

Open-source implementation

- ▶ J.M. Serrano, L. Roca., P. Navarro. “Repository with the implementation source code for modeling, optimization and simulation of a combined cooling system (wet cooling tower, dry cooler and surface condenser) at Plataforma Solar de Almería as part of the SOLhycool research project”. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17882447](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17882447)
- ▶ J.M. Serrano, “Repository with the implementation and results of the modeling and optimization of a solar-driven multi-effect distillation system at Plataforma Solar de Almería”. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17882753](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17882753)
- ▶ J.M. Serrano, Repository with the source code for the PhD thesis manuscript: “Towards optimal resource management in solar thermal applications: CSP and desalination”. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17885527](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17885527)

Towards optimal resource management in solar thermal applications: CSP and desalination

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iGracias!